

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT	DD	MM.MMM	LONG	DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2022	03	06	PUNTA ARENAS	N	-52	28.008	E	-068	24.174
End	2022	04	21	CAPE TOWN	N	-33	54.204	E	018	27.756

SCIENTIFIC INTEREST & CAMPAIGN OBJECTIVES

The *seascape* is composed of a non-linear combination of processes that cover spatial scales from millimeters to thousands of kilometers, on times ranging from seconds to millennia [McWilliams, 2016]. A critical scale is the one associated with major current perturbations, the so-called *mesoscale* and associated *submesoscale processes*, such as eddies, filaments, and fronts. These phenomena are known to impact bulk primary production, mostly via vertical movements that bring nutrients to the photic zone and promote lateral and vertical mixing [Mahadevan 2016, Levy et al., 2018]. However, much less is known about the impact of submesoscale processes on plankton taxonomic and functional diversity and associated vertical export of organic matter [Kavanaugh et al., 2016]. In *Tara* MM, we are addressing the following questions: (a) What is the effect of physical segregation and mixing on competition and exclusion? and (b) Do submesoscale downward and upward vertical fluxes restructure communities by favouring some species, inducing a fast response to the changing environment? Given the ubiquity of meso/submesoscale processes, these unknowns limit our current capacity to model biogeochemical cycles and, more broadly, to constrain the role of the ocean microbiome in a changing climate. The reason behind the lack of knowledge is the ephemeral nature of these phenomena, typically lasting from a few days to a few weeks, and their unpredictable nature, due to the high nonlinearity of the physical processes that cause them. The outcome is a dramatic lack of *in situ* observations of the biological responses. This experiment thus aims to address these observational stumbling blocks by combining recent technological advances in marine biology (-omics) with automated in-line sampling, and state-of-the-art satellite missions in an innovative field experiment.

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PARTICIPANTS

ROLE		NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	Martin HERTAU
2	CREW - 1st Officer	Yves TOURNON
3	CREW - Mecano	Loïc CAUDAN
4	CREW - Deck	François AURAT
5	CREW - Deck	David MONMARCHÉ
6	CREW - Cook	Sophie BIN
7	CREW - Media	
8	GUEST - Artist	

9	GUEST - Observer	
10	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	Alison CHASE
11	SCIENCE - B - W-Lab biogeochemistry	Giancarlo BACHI
12	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	Cora HÖRSTMANN
13	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry	Paula HUBER
14	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	Clara TRELLU
15	SCIENCE - F – Chief Scientist	Rémi LAXENAIRE

ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT & SAMPLING STRATEGY

Overview of the Leg 12

The leg 12 of Tara Mission Microbiomes was remarkable for its length since it lasted 47 days and the Tara covered about 4500 nautical miles. This long voyage (Figure 1) provided an opportunity, through underway sampling in the open ocean (colored lines in Figure 1), to achieve a large-scale oblique transect of surface properties across the fronts of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current and, by joining the southern tips of the South American and African continents, to close the southern boundary of the Atlantic Ocean, which is important in the context of the AtlantECO program. This synoptic sampling was only paused during the three sampling efforts of this leg: Sally Cyclonic Eddy (blue in Figure 1), Front between the Emmy Anticyclonic Eddy and a large meander of the Subtropical front (red in Figure 1) and the St Helena Bay Monitoring Line (green in Figure 1).

Figure 1: Overview of Tara MM Leg12. Underway measurements were active along the coloured portion of Tara's track. The blue, red and green patches indicate the position of Sally Cyclone, Emmy Anticyclone and SHBML sampling efforts respectively. Black contours are ACC fronts computed from DT-2018 version of Mean Dynamical Height (Taburet et al., 2019) using thresholds of Park et al., 2019.

Sampling effort #1: Sally Cyclone

The first sampling effort is composed of four stations across the cyclonic eddy we named Sally, in honor of Sally Poncet, an expert on the South Georgia Island region and friend to the Tara. This cyclone was identified as a large patch of Chlorophyll a (Chla, from CLS's OceanColor maps) lying between Subantarctic and Polar fronts. The origin of this cyclone in November 2021 in water enriched by South Georgia Island (Figure 2) was obtained using the TOEddies algorithm (Laxenaire et al., 2018) applied to the NRT CMEMS DT_2018 altimeter maps (Taburet et al., 2019).

Although the weather in the "Roaring Forties" is not stable, associated with strong winds and transient atmospheric phenomena, a window of a few days of mild weather was expected at the time of the sampling. Because the cyclone had a very particular history and in an area that is not often sampled, we proceeded with sampling despite the knowledge that we would not have time to sample this structure for 15 days as planned for a best-case scenario. We followed the initial strategy of 3 depths (surface, Deep Chlorophyll Maximum (DMC) and meso-pelagic) following the AtlantEco protocol, but the GTR rosette was not working during this sampling.

Figure 2: Weekly averaged Chla at the time when Sally cyclone first appeared. Blue/yellow track indicates the trajectory of the Sally cyclone. Yellow part of this track indicates the last month before the sampling.

Figure 3: Map of the stations across Sally cyclone over Chla averaged during the sampling (left) and Rosette casts in these stations (right).

We started the sampling at an environmental station (#091, Figure 3) away from the structure just north of the Polar Front. We then mapped the structures from southeast to northwest to identify its location. We targeted the outer part of the structure (#092, Figure 3) following altimetry maps, as no clear Chla satellite maps were available at that time, and we also launched 3 drifter buoys. These 3 drifters diverged, indicating that we were not in the main eddy. We identified a different T/S structure from the environment with a significantly lower temperature between 150 and 450 meters and a subsurface intensified Chla. We then targeted the core of the eddy based on the altimetry (#093, Figure 3) and a local maximum of Chla obtained during the mapping. The local temperature minimum was more pronounced but no clear difference in the Chla. We then had to stop for 1 day due to strong wind to wait for an extra day of sampling. During this break, we drifted to the southeast and crossed an increased Chla area associated to a bloom of Diatoms (Figure 3 and #094 in Figure 4) that most likely corresponded to the cyclone that drifted east during our sampling because of the Subantarctic Front. Thus, we decided to change the sampling plan and targeted the center of this high patch (#094, Figure 3). We sampled a clear interior of the eddy with a clear high DCM and a significant low temperature.

Figure 4: First page of a given sample from the Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB) during the four stations of sampling of Sally cyclone.

Sampling effort #2: Subtropical front between Emmy anticyclone and a large meander

After the first sampling effort, we made the decision to look for the next promising structures in the Cape Cauldron (southwestern part of the Walvis Ridge as defined by Boebel et al., 2003). This choice was motivated by the identification, from satellite maps, of numerous dynamic structures in this region (which explains its name) and the fact that the weather is more favorable for several days of sampling in a row since it is further north.

Figure 5: Extract from Operational tool of the area of interest with the different structures the 07/03/2022. The background is 5 days averaged Chla (no colorbar in Kml format in the Operational Tool) and the different structures are indicated. C and A correspond, respectively, to the position of cyclones and anticyclones.

We identified a particularly interesting association of structures (Figure 5) where the subtropical front (STF, synoptic scale) is composed of three eddies and a meander (mesoscale) forming intense filaments and fronts (submesoscale). We followed the dynamics of this structure and defined three different scenarios depending on the front and eddies we were going to sample. The main idea, shared between the three scenarios, was to conduct two surface stations (one to the south and one to the north of the area of interest), conduct two depth characterizations within the boundary of the selected front of interest (either eddies or meanders), and conduct a section of high-frequency surface stations across the front. For this effort whose goal was to analyze the close link between biological communities and physics, we prioritized the OMICS and BGC protocols.

This sampling effort therefore began with a surface station south of the STF (#095) to characterize surface properties away from this dynamic region. We then mapped, using underway measurement and surface drifters, from a cyclone (C1 in Figure 5) to an anticyclone (A1 in Figure 5) to test the feasibility of studying a thin, but persistent, filament (Tongue 1 in Figure 5) composed of water from south of the STF advected between two eddies. Unfortunately, this filament was very thin. So, we opted for plan B to study the front between a large anticyclone from Atlantic Ocean, which we named Emmy (A1 in Figure 5), and a large meander (Tongue 2 in Figure 5) where water from south of the STF are advected northward.

The sampling of the front area began with the Emmy Anticyclone (#096). It was associated with a thick mixed layer (ML) with strong positive temperature anomalies. The front was crossed overnight and a similar 2-depth station was conducted in the meander (#097). Thanks to the first two days, we identified the limits of the front and characterized it as a massive temperature jump of nearly 3°C at the surface in only a few kilometers. We then began high-resolution sampling of the front planned as three surface stations and two surface+DCM stations. After the surface station (#098), we conducted the first surface + DCM station (#099). The CTD profiles revealed a very interesting vertical structure with regions of near-surface mixing over water like that in the Emmy anticyclone. We thus suppressed the surface stations and conducted another surface + DCM station more on the side of the front (#100). We then spent one night doing surface mapping along a rectangular shape to gain insight into the geometric and temporal variability of the front at the surface. For the next day across the front, we limited ourselves to 2 surface stations + DCM (#101 and 102) but, as we get rid of the surface-only stations, we added protocols such as decknet in the DCM.

Figure 6: Map of the stations of this effort zoomed on the frontal area over Chla averaged during the sampling (left) and Rosette casts in these stations (right).

The following night was devoted to a TIA transect started as far southeast as possible to maximize the possibility of crossing the front (many variations identified from the TSG) while considering the lowest possible speed (and thus the depth of the TIA) and the need to be early in the morning at the center of the Emmy anticyclone. This transect (Figure 7) allowed us to characterize the change in property from meander to eddy with a cold filament and the sloping structure of the front.

Figure 7: TIA transect from the meander (cold, east) to the anticyclone (warm, west). A cold filament was crossed between 6.6 and 6.7° East. Figure provided by Heineke Martina (Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon).

We then, again, sampled the core of the Emmy eddy (#103) and took the opportunity to do a GTR cast since it was functional at this point. We then left the area by crossing the meander taking profit of the underway measurement.

We then chose to conduct a two-depth station (#104) in a cyclonic eddy called Sophie (C2 in Figure 5) north of the front. Altimetry maps were not clear at the time, but they indicated that it was either associated with a previous meander or related to an eddy coming from the north. In either case, it was an excellent candidate for TARA MM sampling, either linked to the Emmy/Meander sampling effort or to the legs along the southwest coast of Africa. We took the opportunity to conduct a new GTR sampling. Finally, as we left the area, we conducted surface sampling (#105) north of the structure as planned.

Sampling effort #3: St Helena Bay Monitoring Line

This leg was completed with four stations distributed between upwelling, shelf break and ocean fronts in St. Helena Bay. Defining the location of these stations was easier than for the previous two efforts

as this sampling is part of a monitoring of the area with a fixed station location. From shore (#106) to open ocean (#109), a clear gradient of Chl_a has been recorded (see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Map of the stations across St Helena Bay Monitoring Line over Chl_a averaged during the sampling (left) and Fluorescence in Rosette casts in these stations (right).

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MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS

This leg is already successful as we have sampled the core of three eddies (two cyclones and one anticyclone), one meander and the associated fronts (edges of the eddies and a subtropical front between an anticyclone and a cold meander) at a fairly high frequency. The results should reveal much information about the response of the biological community to these physical processes.

For the cyclone Sally, unfortunately, it was advected by a front during the sampling period while it remained in place for the previous weeks. As a result, we did not have a clear signal when mapping, so we had to change our plan. Since we were well prepared, we adapted our plan with 4 stations across the eddy allowing an interesting section through this eddy between the outer and the center. This eddy was associated with a near-surface bloom while this structure was clearly intensified in the subsurface with a core below 200 m. We have taken the opportunity to accurately sample both this surface community and those in the core of the eddy, which will be an excellent opportunity to study the isolation of the eddy core from the environment and to try to understand how this eddy can promote a surface bloom while being clearly intensified in the subsurface. We can already, thanks to the IFCB images (Figure 4), suppose that there is more diversity on the outside of the structure than in its center where a diatom bloom clearly dominates.

For Emmy and the meander, the new insights expected from this week of sampling on the link between the biological community and meso-/sub-mesoscale processes are numerous. The front was particularly strong, well characterized in both its temporal and geographic properties from underway surface measurements and a TIA transect with a clear cold filament that is, to our knowledge, the first in-situ record. CTD profiles across the front showed a mixed layer above either water from the meander or from the anticyclone. With the characterization of OMICS in the mixed layer and below it, we expect to have new information on the impact of subscale processes both on the vertical, by

comparing the communities between layer in each station, and on the lateral mixing by comparing the stations between them. We also have a lot of expectations on results of proteomics and metagenomics sample to characterize how the communities typical of either the anticyclone or the meander are modified when they are in the frontal zone which is particularly dynamic.

For the St. Helena Bay Monitoring Line, we sampled four stations across the slope. Our sampling clearly indicates the Chl_a gradient that is maximal near the coast and then decreases toward the open ocean. It should be noted that the bloom in this bay is known to be associated with an oxygen minimum near the coast. Since, during sampling, massive numbers of dead lobsters and sharks were found on the beach in this bay, this indicates that this bloom created a strong oxygen minimum and was therefore intense.

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 091

Station Title: Environment Cyclone Sally

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/03/22 08h20	09 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/03/22 08h38	57 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/03/22 08h56	11 min	Rosette cast #1	0-3	To avoid Pump Contamination	1	1				1
2022/03/22 09h36	37 min	VMP250 #1	0-200		1					1
2022/03/22 10h41	10 min	WP11 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/03/22 11h26	21 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/03/22 12h05	11 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/03/22 12h53	22 min	Rosette cast #3	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		1
2022/03/22 14h03	17 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/03/22 15h23	17 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/03/22 17h06	42 min	WP11 20 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	
2022/03/22 18h43	1 h 42 min	Rosette cast #4	0-1000	MESO	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/03/22 20h50	1 h 10 min	Rosette cast #5	0-1000	MESO	1	1	1	1		1
2022/03/22 22h14	24 min	WP11 200 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	
2022/03/22 23h14	31 min	VMP250 #2	0-200		1					1

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 092

Station Title: Border Cyclone Sally

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/03/23 00h01	21 h 49 min	TIA	0-50		1					1
2022/03/23 23h20		Drifter		# 180	1					1
2022/03/24 06h42		Drifter		# 174	1					1
2022/03/24 07h21		Drifter		# 171	1					1
2022/03/24 07h49		Drifter		# 172	1					1
2022/03/24 08h16		Drifter		# 178	1					1
2022/03/24 08h39	35 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/03/24 08h44	10 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/03/24 08h51	06 min	Rosette cast #1	0-3	To avoid Pump Contamination	1	1				1
2022/03/24 09h14	21 min	VMP250 #1	0-200		1					1
2022/03/24 09h57	10 min	WPII 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/03/24 10h38	31 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/03/24 09h57	12 min	Secchi Disk	0-50	SRF			1			
2022/03/24 11h40	12 min	WPII 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/03/24 12h38	23 min	Rosette cast #3	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		1
2022/03/24 13h30	30 min	SML	0-3	SRF			1	1		
2022/03/24 13h35	12 min	hTSRB	0-3	SRF	1					
2022/03/24 14h00	1h	Manta 330 net	0	SRF	1				1	
2022/03/24 15h15	14 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/03/24 15h38	15 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/03/24 16h23	1 h 07 min	Rosette cast #4	0-1000	MESO	1	1	1	1		1
2022/03/24 18h52	20 min	WPII 200 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	
2022/03/24 19h45	1 h 01 min	Rosette cast #5	0-1000	MESO	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/03/24 21h00	17 min	VMP250 #2	0-200		1					1

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 093

Station Title: In the Cyclone Sally

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/03/24 23h10		Drifter		# 169	1					1
2022/03/25 00h06		Drifter		# 184	1					1
2022/03/25 01h00		Drifter		# 176	1					1
2022/03/25 07h22		Drifter		# 170	1					1
2022/03/25 07h36		Drifter		# 179	1					1
2022/03/25 08h02		Drifter		# 173	1					1
2022/03/25 08h30	10 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/03/25 08h41	49 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/03/25 08h53	14 min	Rosette cast #1	0-3	To avoid Pump Contamination	1	1				1
2022/03/25 09h27	25 min	VMP250 #1	0-200		1					1
2022/03/25 10h38	10 min	WP11 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/03/25 10h58	10 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/03/25 11h47	6 min	Secchi Disk	0-50	SRF			1			
2022/03/25 11h52	27 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/03/25 13h02	20 min	Rosette cast #3	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		1
2022/03/25 13h38	11 min	hTSRB	0-3	SRF	1					
2022/03/25 14h00	1h	Manta 330 net	0	SRF	1					1
2022/03/25 15h27	1 h 06 min	Rosette cast #4	0-1000	MESO	1	1	1	1		1
2022/03/25 15h55	21 min	SML	0-3	SRF			1	1		
2022/03/25 17h00	15 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/03/25 17h21	18 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/03/25 17h59	1 h 01 min	WP11 20 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	
2022/03/25 19h59	1 h 05 min	WP11 200 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	
2022/03/25 21h38	1 h 30 min	Rosette cast #5	0-1000	MESO	1	1	1	1	1	1

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 094

Station Title: Core of the Cyclone Sally

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/03/27 10h05	18 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/03/27 10h43	21 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/03/27 11h28	11 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/03/27 12h03	1 h 28 min	WP11 200 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	
2022/03/27 13h33	10 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/03/27 14h17	27 min	WP11 20 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	
2022/03/27 15h02	08 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/03/27 15h03	36 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/03/27 15h17	06 min	Rosette cast #1	0-3	To avoid Pump Contamination	1	1				1
2022/03/27 15h40	07 min	hTSRB	0-3	SRF	1					
2022/03/27 16h31	24 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/03/27 17h17	43 min	VMP250 #1	0-200		1					1
2022/03/27 18h29	1 h 02 min	Rosette cast #3	0-1000	MESO	1	1	1	1		1
2022/03/27 20h41	43 min	Rosette cast #4	0-1000	MESO	1	1	1	1	1	1

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 095

Station Title: Surface south of Subtropical Front

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/04 13h48	44 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF		1	1	1	1	

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 096

Station Title: Core of the Anticyclone Emmy #1

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/05 19h14		Drifter		# 186	1					1
2022/04/05 19h42	12 h 27 min	TIA	0-50		1					1
2022/04/05 21h53		Drifter		# 183	1					1
2022/04/05 22h37		Drifter		# 177	1					1
2022/04/06 00h00		Drifter		# 175	1					1
2022/04/06 01h14		Drifter		# 120	1					1
2022/04/06 02h12		Drifter		# 185	1					1
2022/04/06 03h31		Drifter		# 167	1					1
2022/04/06 08h14		Drifter		# 168	1					1
2022/04/06 08h44	08 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/04/06 09h02	39 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/04/06 09h16	06 min	Rosette cast #1	0-3	To avoid Pump Contamination	1	1				1
2022/04/06 10h09	1 h 06 min	VMP250 #1	0-200		1					1
2022/04/06 12h10	10 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/06 12h39	10 min	WP11 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/06 13h11	26 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		1
2022/04/06 14h23	17 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/04/06 14h48	18 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/04/06 15h22	24 min	WP11 20 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	
2022/04/06 16h39	18 min	WP11 200 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	
2022/04/06 17h23	43 min	VMP250 #2	0-200		1					1

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 097

Station Title: In the Meander

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/06 19h35	9 h 53 min	TIA	0-50		1					1
2022/04/07 05h54	07 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/04/07 06h10	34 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/04/07 06h21	11 min	Rosette cast #1	0-3	To avoid Pump Contamination	1	1				1
2022/04/07 06h47	44 min	VMP250 #1	0-200		1					1
2022/04/07 08h06	11 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/07 08h35	11 min	WP11 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/07 09h14	21 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		1
2022/04/07 09h52	16 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/04/07 10h14	14 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/04/07 10h43	1h	Manta 330 net	0	SRF	1					1
2022/04/07 12h10	14 min	WP11 200 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	
2022/04/07 13h04	1h 02 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/04/07 14h38	41 min	WP11 20 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	
2022/04/07 15h27	1 h 03 min	VMP250 #2	0-200		1					1

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 098

Station Title: Cross Front #1

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/07 19h49	10 h 31 min	TIA	0-50		1					1
2022/04/07 06h24	42 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 099

Station Title: Cross Front #2

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/08 09h20	10 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/04/08 09h20	33 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/04/08 09h20	11 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/08 10h06	11 min	WP11 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/08 10h48	25 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		
2022/04/08 11h44	1 h 02 min	VMP250 #1	0-200		1					1

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 100

Station Title: Cross Front #3

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/08 14h40	09 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/04/08 15h00	30 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/04/08 15h05	10 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/08 15h51	10 min	WP11 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/08 16h35	26 min	Rosette cast #1	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		
2022/04/08 17h43	40 min	VMP250 #1	0-200		1					1

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 101

Station Title: Cross Front #4

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/09 06h04	06 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/04/09 06h19	31 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/04/09 06h32	10 min	WP11 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/09 07h04	10 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/09 07h52	23 min	Rosette cast #1	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/04/09 08h46	31 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		1
2022/04/09 09h42	1 h 05 min	VMP250 #1	0-200		1					1

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 102

Station Title: Cross Front #5

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/09 12h22	08 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/04/09 12h35	30 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/04/09 12h37	11 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/09 13h11	11 min	WP11 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/09 13h54	24 min	Rosette cast #1	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/04/09 14h50	24 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		1
2022/04/09 15h34	1 h 07 min	VMP250 #1	0-200		1					1

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 103

Station Title: Core of the Anticyclone Emmy #2

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/09 19h27	10 h 42 min	TIA	0-50		1					1
2022/04/10 07h00	10 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/04/10 07h32	39 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/04/10 07h36	06 min	Rosette cast #1	0-3	To avoid Pump Contamination	1	1				1
2022/04/10 08h10	1 h 10 min	VMP250 #1	0-200		1					1
2022/04/10 09h44	10 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/10 10h08	10 min	WP11 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/10 10h51	59 min	Rosette cast #2	0-1000	MESO	1	1	1	1		1
2022/04/10 12h16	30 min	WP11 200 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	
2022/04/10 13h18	49 min	WP11 20 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	
2022/04/10 16h31	45 min	GTR cast #1	0-1000		1	1				1

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 104

Station Title: Core of the Cyclone Sophie

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/12 05h07	06 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/04/12 05h31	1 h 14 min	Rosette cast #1	0-1000	MESO	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/04/12 07h23	25 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		1
2022/04/12 08h23	10 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/12 08h51	10 min	WP11 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/12 09h08	45 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/04/12 10h28	27 min	GTR cast #1	0-1000		1	1				1

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 105

Station Title: Surface north of Subtropical Front

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/13 11h12	33 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF		1	1	1	1	

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 106

Station Title: SHBML Inshore Station

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/16 05h54	03 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/04/16 05h59	46 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/04/16 06h10	06 min	Rosette cast #1	0-3	To avoid Pump Contamination	1	1				1
2022/04/16 06h34	10 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/16 07h04	06 min	WP11 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/16 08h19	13 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/04/16 08h42	16 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/04/16 09h34	32 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		1
2022/04/16 10h23	12 min	hTSRB	0-3	SRF	1					
2022/04/16 11h12	21 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/04/16 11h19	17 min	Secchi Disk	0-50	SRF			1			
2022/04/16 12h47	26 min	GTR cast #1	0-1000		1	1				1
2022/04/16 14h34	34 min	SML	0-3	SRF			1	1		

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 107

Station Title: SHBML Shelf Break Front

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/17 05h05	03 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/04/17 05h08	25 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/04/17 05h19	07 min	Rosette cast #1	0-3	To avoid Pump Contamination	1	1				1
2022/04/17 05h45	29 min	VMP250 #1	0-200		1					1
2022/04/17 06h33	06 min	WP11 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/17 07h15	42 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/04/17 08h35	34 min	Rosette cast #3	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		1
2022/04/17 09h25	11 min	Rosette cast #4	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		1
2022/04/17 10h07	38 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/04/17 10h59	44 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/04/17 11h41	53 min	SML	0-3	SRF			1	1		
2022/04/17 12h26	12 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/17 13h20	35 min	Rosette cast #5	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/04/17 14h32	24 min	Rosette cast #6	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		1
2022/04/17 15h57	26 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/04/17 16h16	24 min	GTR cast #1	0-1000		1	1				1
2022/04/17 16h54	37 min	GTR cast #2	0-1000		1	1				1

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 108

Station Title: SHBML SAMW

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/19 05h13	09 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/04/19 05h46	39 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/04/19 05h58	10 min	Rosette cast #1	0-3	To avoid Pump Contamination	1	1				1
2022/04/19 06h23	51 min	VMP250 #1	0-200		1					1
2022/04/19 07h40	11 min	WP11 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/19 08h27	23 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/04/19 09h24	25 min	Rosette cast #3	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		1
2022/04/19 10h24	36 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/04/19 11h26	29 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/04/19 12h45	10 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/19 13h36	29 min	Rosette cast #4	0-1000	MESO	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/04/19 14h34	27 min	Rosette cast #5	0-1000	MESO	1	1	1	1		1
2022/04/19 15h26	06 min	VMP250 #2	0-200		1					1

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 109

Station Title: SHBML Ocean Front

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
2022/04/20 05h24	01 min	BowPole	0			1				1
2022/04/20 05h26	39 min	A20 pump	0-3	SRF			1	1	1	
2022/04/20 05h30	06 min	Rosette cast #1	0-3	To avoid Pump Contamination	1	1				1
2022/04/20 05h50	1 h 10 min	VMP250 #1	0-200		1					1
2022/04/20 07h15	11 min	WP11 20 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/20 07h47	09 min	Secchi Disk	0-50	SRF			1			
2022/04/20 07h54	27 min	Rosette cast #2	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/04/20 08h54	24 min	Rosette cast #3	0-200	EPI	1	1	1	1		1
2022/04/20 09h35	18 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/04/20 10h12	20 min	Régent 680 net	0-200	EPI Vertical/oblique	1			1	1	1
2022/04/20 11h00	18 min	hTSRB	0-3	SRF	1					
2022/04/20 11h37	11 min	WP11 200 horiz	0-3	SRF	1			1	1	1
2022/04/20 12h18	22 min	SML	0-3	SRF			1	1		
2022/04/20 12h18	27 min	Rosette cast #4	0-1000	MESO	1	1	1	1	1	1
2022/04/20 14h53	1 h 20 min	Rosette cast #6	0-1000	MESO (cast #5 did not work)	1	1	1	1		1

INVENTORY OF SAMPLES COLLECTED DURING THE CAMPAIGN

	Storage T°C	RT+10	RT+10	RT+10	FRG+4	FRG+4	FRG+4	FRZ-20	FRZ-20	FRZ-20	LN-80	LN-80	LN-80
	Box size	B-Box	G-box	XXL	W-box-S	W-box-M	W-box-L	W-box-S	W-box-M	W-box-L	Dewar #1	Dewar #2	Dewar #3
Protocol	Container type												
DGAS	ExeV-12mL						159						
DIC13	200-mL-Bottle		36										
DICTA	500-mL-bottle		27										
DO18	AmberV-40mL	8		34									
NUT-1	20mLCryoV	17								99			
NUT-2	20mLCryoV							8					
SAL	125-mL Bottle			62									
DINO	60-mL-Bottle									120			
HG-M	125-mL Bottle			25									
HG-T	40-mL-Bottle			8									
MTE-T	60-mL-Bottle			34									
MTE-F	60-mL-Bottle			8									
MB320	4-mL-Vial							55					
MB023	4-mL-Vial							55					
MB<02	50-mL-falcon								55				
eDNA	sterivex								28				
NP550	20-mL-vial								26				
NP045	4-mL-Vial							26					
HG	Zip-lock	26											
PM	Zip-lock	41											
S320	5-mL-cryotube										70		
S023	5-mL-cryotube										71		
S<02	5-mL-cryotube					71							
P320	5-mL-cryotube										42		
P023	5-mL-cryotube										42		
HP	2-mL-cryotube											116	
SG	5-mL-cryotube										192		
FC	2-mL-cryotube											2	311
HC	2-mL-cryotube											291	
SEM	petri-slide	44											
FM20	50-mL-falcon				23								
E20	15-mL-falcon								22				
S20	5-mL-cryotube										22		

S20-L	5-mL-falcon							22					
PM-HG20	Zip-lock	22											
MB20	4-mL-Vial							22					
CP50	petri-slide	22											
SCP50	petri-slide												
F200	250-mL-bottle		25										
E200	15-mL-falcon								23				
S200	5-mL-cryotube										23		
S200-L	5-mL-falcon							23					
PM-HG200	Zip-lock	23											
MB200	4-mL-Vial							23					
CP200	petri-slide												
F680	250-mL-bottle		10										
F2000	250-mL-bottle		11										
E680	15-mL-falcon								10				
S680-L	MULTIPLATES									10			
E2000	15-mL-falcon								10				
AI	petri-slide	106											
AS	2-mL-cryotube												106
AF	Zip-lock									106			
SP300	2-mL-cryotube												13
MP300	2-mL-cryotube							1					
CP300	petri-slide	5											
TOC	30-mL-bottle									10			
SSML-PC	2-mL-cryotube												5
SSML-PT	2-mL-cryotube												5
S025-L	15-mL-falcon								41				
S520-L	5-mL-falcon							43					
FM5	5-mL-falcon				45								
TOTAL		314	109	172	68	71	159	278	215	345	462	432	417

	Storage T°C	RT+10	RT+10	RT+10	FRG+4	FRG+4	FRG+4	FRZ-20	FRZ-20	FRZ-20	LN-80	LN-80	LN-80
	Box size	B-Box	G-box	XXL	W-box-S	W-box-M	W-box-L	W-box-S	W-box-M	W-box-L	Dewar #1	Dewar #2	Dewar #3
Protocol	Container type												
DOC+CDOM+FDOM	40-mL-Vial							22					